

STUDIES IN THE MICHAEL CONDENSATION. PART III.
 SYNTHESIS OF 1-HYDROXY-2:4b-DIMETHYL-7-KETO-
 1:2:3:4:4a:4b:5:6:7:9:10:10a-DODECAHYDRO-
 PHENANTHRENE

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The trimethyl heptane-1:3:7-tricarboxylate, on the Dieckmann cyclisation, methylation, bromination, dehydrobromination, hydrolysis and decarboxylation furnishes β -(2-keto-3-methylcyclohex- $\Delta^{1:6}$ -enyl)-propionic acid. The methyl ester of the latter, on the Michael condensation, hydrolysis and esterification, affords methyl β -(2-keto-3-methyl-6-methylacetate-cyclohexyl)-propionate, which on the Dieckmann cyclisation, followed by acid treatment, yields 2-methyldecalin-1:6-dione. Methyl β -(2-keto-3-methyl-6-ethyl cyanoacetate-cyclohexyl)-propionate, on methylation, followed by the above series of reactions, furnishes 2:5-dimethyldecalin-1:6 dione. The latter, on treatment with ethylene-glycol, lithium aluminium hydride and acid, furnishes 1-hydroxy-2:5-dimethyl-decal-6-one, which with the methiodide of 1-diethylaminobutan-3-one yields 1-hydroxy-2:4b-dimethyl-7-keto-1:2:3:4:4a:4b:5:6:7:9:10:10a-dodecahydrophenanthrene (III).

In the classical synthesis of cholesterol, Robinson and his collaborators (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1855; 1953, 361; 1955, 3348) have utilised Reich's diketone (I) (Reich, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1945, 28, 892) as a relay. During the conversion of the diketone (I) into the Köster-Logemann ketone (II) (*Ber.*, 1940, 73, 299), Robinson *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 361) have prepared (+) 1-hydroxy-2:4b-dimethyl-7-keto-1:2:3:4:4a:4b:5:6:7:9:10:10a-dodecahydrophenanthrene (III). In an attempt to synthesise Reich's diketone, the synthesis of (III) by the application of the Mannich-Robinson reaction on the hydroxy-ketone (XIV) has been achieved in the following way.

The conversion of methyl β -(1-carbomethoxy-2-ketocyclohexyl)-propionate (Howarth and Mavin, *ibid.*, 1933, 1012) to methyl β -(2-keto-3-methyl-3-carbomethoxycyclohex- $\Delta^{1:6}$ -enyl)-propionate was effected according to the method of Sen Gupta and Bhattacharyya (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 337). The above saturated β -keto ester was cleaved with sodium ethoxide and then hydrolysed and esterified to furnish the trimethyl ester (IV), which was cyclised with sodium and methylated *in situ* to afford the substituted β -keto ester (V: R=H). The latter on treatment with bromine gave a crystalline bromo compound (V: R=Br), which on treatment with dimethylaniline furnished the unsaturated compound (VI). The latter on heating with a mixture of acetic and hydrochloric acids gave crystalline β -(2-keto-3-methylcyclohex- $\Delta^{1:6}$ -enyl)-propionic acid. The mother-liquor of the crystalline bromo compound furnished a heavy oil which, on similar treatments, furnished the same crystalline acid (VII: R=H).

The Michael condensation of the ester (VI) with ethyl cyanoacetate yielded the adduct (VIII). The methyl ester of the acid (VII: R=H) was condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate as well as with diethyl malonate, according to the method of Banerjee and Bhattacharyya (this issue, p. 457) to afford the condensation products (IX: R=Me; R₁=H; R₂=CN; R₃=Et and R=Me; R₁=H; R₂=CO₂Et; R₃=Et) respectively. Subsequent to the completion of our work (Bhattacharyya and Banerjee, *Science & Culture*, 1957, 23, 45, 107) Aebli and Grob (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1957, 40, 2185) have reported the synthesis of ethyl β-(2-keto 3-methyl-3-carbethoxy-cyclohex-Δ^{1:6}-enyl)-propionate by a different route. In contrary to our observation, the Swiss authors were unable to hydrolyse this unsaturated ester with either acid or alkali. They have successfully condensed diethyl malonate with this unsaturated compound to produce ethyl β-(2-keto-3-methyl-3-carbethoxy-6-diethyl malonate-cyclohexyl)-propionate in an excellent yield. The latter compound, on treatment with alkali, furnishes the acid (VII: R=H) properties of which agree with those of our preparation.

The compound (IX: R=Me; R₁=H; R₂=CN; R₃=Et) was hydrolysed and decarboxylated with acid and then esterified to furnish the dimethyl ester (IX: R=R₃=Me; R₁=R₂=H) which, on cyclisation with sodium followed by acid treatment, afforded the diketone (XII: R=H). The latter was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride to the crystalline diol (XIII: R=H) which, on dehydration with potassium hydrogen sulphate, followed by dehydrogenation, yielded 2-methylnaphthalene.

The above cyano-ester (IX: R=Me; R₁=H; R₂=CN; R₃=Et) was methylated according to the procedure of Banerjee and Bhattacharyya (*loc. cit.*) and the resulting product was converted into the dimethyl ester (IX: R=R₁=R₃=Me; R₂=H) which was cyclised with sodium hydride and then hydrolysed and decarboxylated with acid to yield the diketone (XII: R=Me). This diketone, on reduction with the same reagent, gave presumably a mixture of epimeric diols (XIII: R=Me) from which a pure crystalline component was isolated. The epimeric diols were converted into 2:5-dimethylnaphthalene.

It may be mentioned that the crude dicarboxylic acid (IX: R=R₂=R₃=H; R₁=Me) on pyrolysis with lead carbonate furnished the expected product (XII: R=Me), but the acid (IX: R=R₁=R₂=R₃=H) on similar treatment failed to furnish any ketonic material.

Even, if the Michael addition to an αβ-unsaturated cyclic ketone is axial (Corey, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 1044; Johnson, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1956, 167) in cases of simple cyclohexanones having a substituent at C₆, the ring may flip over and then enolise to produce the thermodynamically stable *trans* compounds (e, e) (Bachmann and Fornefeld, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 5529; Ginsberg and Pappo, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 938; Corey, *loc. cit.*). The compounds represented by structures (IX) and (VIII), probably, have *trans* configurations. The resulting diketones (XII: R=H and R=Me) from the di-esters (IX: R=R₃=Me; R₁=R₂=H and R=R₁=R₂=Me; R₃=H), also have *trans* ring-fusion (Hückel *et al.*, *Annalen* 1925, 441, 1).

With a view to preparing the diketone (XII: R=Me) with the keto group at C₁ protected, the dimethyl ester (IX: R=R₁=R₂=Me; R₃=H) was treated with ethylene-glycol in presence of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (Salmi, *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 1803; Beyler and Sarett, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 1397; Lukes, Poos and Sarett, *ibid.*, 1952, 74, 1401; Mukherjee, Gandhi and Vig, *this Journal*, 1956, 33, 853), but unfortunately, the compound (X) could be isolated in a very poor yield. The sodium salt of the crude dicarboxylic acid (IX: R=R₁=R₂=H; R₃=Me) was treated with sodium borohydride, and the crude hydroxy-dicarboxylic acid was esterified with diazomethane to yield the compound (XI). This hydroxy-ester could be cyclised neither by sodium in benzene nor by sodium ethoxide in ethanol. The observations that 2-methyldecalin-1:6-dione and 2:5-dimethyldecalin-1:6 dione furnished a mono-semicarbazone and a mono 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone respectively under usual conditions led us to conclude that the keto group at C₁ was more hindered than that at C₆. The semicarbazone of the diketone (XII: R=Me), prepared in the usual way, was reduced with sodium borohydride (cf Taub, Hoffmann and Wendler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 452) in ethanol, and the resulting product, when hydrolysed with a solution of oxalic acid, yielded the hydroxy compound (XIV) in extremely poor yield. This hydroxy compound was prepared in a better yield by treating the diketone (XII: R=Me) with ethyleneglycol and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (cf. Herzog *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1953, 75, 4425), followed by lithium aluminium hydride and acid. That the hydroxy compound has the structure (XIV), is clearly indicated by its smooth condensation with ethyl formate in presence of sodium methoxide. The crude formylated product was converted into the methylanilinoethylene compound and then subjected to the Mannich-Robinson reaction with methiodide of 1-diethylaminobutan-3-one in presence of potassium *tert.*-butoxide (Robinson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 53; 1952, 1224; 1955, 3341; Wilds *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 5794; Sarett *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1953, 75, 422; Banerjee, Chatterjee and Bhattacharyya, *ibid.*, 1955, 77, 408) to yield, after successive treatments with acid and base, 1-hydroxy 2:4b-dimethyl-7-keto-1:2:3:4:4a:4b:5:6:7:9:10:10a-dodecahydrophenanthrene (III) as a pale yellow viscous material in extremely poor yield, characterised through a deep orange crystalline 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. The presence of an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated carbonyl function in the tricyclic hydroxy-ketone (III) is clearly indicated by the ultraviolet data of the compound and its D.N.P. The stereochemistry of the product is under investigation:

(VIII)

(IX)

(X)

(XI)

(XII)

(XIII)

(XIV)

EXPERIMENTAL*

Trimethyl Heptane-1:3:7-tricarboxylate (IV).—Sukh Dev and Rai (this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 266) described the preparation of ethyl β -(1-carbethoxy-2-ketocyclohexyl)-propionate in ethanolic solution without any experimental detail. It has been observed that the yield of the condensation product is considerably lowered if the reaction temperature is not maintained as described below.

To a cold solution of ethyl *cyclohexanone* carboxylate (170 g.) and sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (0.6 g.) and absolute ethanol (120 c.c.), was added dropwise, during 30 minutes, methyl acrylate (86 g.) with vigorous shaking. The reaction mixture gradually turned yellowish and then brown-red. During the addition the temperature was not allowed to rise above 40°. The reaction was allowed to proceed at 30-35° for 12 hrs. The reddish brown reaction mixture was poured in cold dilute acetic acid and worked up with ether to furnish the desired product (216 g.), b.p. 170-80°/5 mm.

* All m.p.'s. and b.p.'s. are uncorrected. The U.V. absorption spectrum was determined in 95% ethanol by the Unicam spectrophotometer S.P. 500. Analyses of a few compounds were done by Mrs. C. Dutta in the micro-analytical Laboratory of the University College of Science and Technology, Calcutta.

To a hot (55-60°) suspension of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (1.85 g.) and absolute ethanol (23 c.c.), was added the above substituted β -keto ester (104 g.) with shaking, when considerable heat was generated and the reaction mixture turned brown. It was heated on a water-bath for 3½ hrs. The cooled dark brown reaction mixture was poured into iced dilute sulphuric acid and the precipitated oil was worked up with ether and distilled, b.p. 190-95°/5 mm, yield 101 g. The latter was refluxed with 6N-HCl (600 c.c.) for 25 hours, when a clear solution was obtained. After removal of the volatile acids, the dried residue was refluxed with a mixture of absolute methanol (225 c.c.) and H₂SO₄ (30 c.c., *d* 1.84) for 35 hours. The cooled reaction mixture was poured into iced water and the precipitated oil was worked up with ether. After removal of the ether, the residue was distilled, b.p. 150-55°/0.8 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4440, yield 72 g. (Found: C, 56.50; H, 8.08. C₁₃H₂₂O₆ requires C, 56.90; H, 8.09%).

Methyl β -(2-Keto-3-methyl-3-carbomethoxy-cyclohexyl)-propionate (V: R=H).—A mixture of sodium dust (9.2 g.), dry benzene (250 c.c.), the tri-ester (IV, 55 g.) and absolute methanol (0.2 c.c.) was refluxed in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 6 hrs. The dark brown reaction mixture was cooled in an ice-salt bath and then treated with methyl iodide (35 c.c.) with occasional shaking for 1½ hrs. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 16 hours and after addition of a further quantity of methyl iodide (10 c.c.), it was refluxed for 6 hrs. The cooled reaction mixture was poured into iced water (600 c.c.) containing H₂SO₄ (2 c.c.). The benzene layer was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted twice with ether-benzene mixture. The combined extract was washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the residue was distilled, b.p. 135-40°/0.7 mm, yield 35.8 g. (Found: C, 60.61; H, 7.85. C₁₃H₂₀O₆ requires C, 60.94; H, 7.84%).

Methyl β -(1-Bromo-2-keto-3-methyl-3-carbomethoxy-cyclohexyl)-propionate (V: R=Br).—To a solution of the substituted β -keto ester (26 g.) in dry CCl₄ (25 c.c.), cooled to 0-5°, was added dropwise a solution of bromine (6.4 c.c.) in dry CCl₄ (7 c.c.). After the completion of addition, the faint red reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 15 minutes in the cooling bath. The solvent and hydrogen bromide were removed under reduced pressure (water pump) at 60-70°. The residue was treated with petroleum ether (30 c.c., 40-60°) when a heavy oil separated. This was left in the refrigerator for 48 hours when a solid (11.5 g.) separated out, m.p. 65-70°. On concentration of the mother-liquor, a further quantity of the same product (0.5 g.), m.p. 65-70°, was obtained. The compound was crystallised thrice from petroleum ether (40-60°) to furnish colorless crystals, m.p. 78°. (Found: Br, 23.34. C₁₃H₁₉O₆Br requires Br, 23.84%).

The dry heavy oil, obtained from the mother-liquors, responded strongly to the Beilstein test and contained a considerable quantity of the desired bromo compound, as shown below.

Methyl β -(2-Keto-3-methyl-3-carbomethoxy-cyclohex- $\Delta^{1:4}$ -enyl)-propionate (VI).—A mixture of the above crude bromo compound (m.p. 65-70°, 10 g.) and freshly

distilled dimethylaniline (10 c.c.) was heated at 155-65° for 30 mins. The reaction mixture was cooled rapidly and, while still mobile, poured into iced HCl and worked up to furnish the desired product (5.6 g.), b.p. 130-35°/0.4 mm; n_D^{25} 1.4772; λ_{max} 235 μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.71). (Found: C, 61.09; H, 7.30. $C_{13}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 61.42; H, 7.12%).

A mixture of the above oily bromo compound (16 g.) and dimethylaniline (14 c.c.) was heated and worked up to give the same unsaturated compound (9.5 g.), b.p. 135-40°/0.5 mm, n_D^{25} 1.4775; λ_{max} 235 μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.61). (Found: C, 61.30; H, 7.57. $C_{13}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 61.42; H, 7.12%).

The above unsaturated keto-ester was also directly prepared from the semi-solid bromo compound, obtained by bromination, in 70% yield.

β -(2-Keto-3-methyl-cyclohex- $\Delta^{1:5}$ -enyl)-propionic Acid (VII: R=H).—A mixture of the above unsaturated substituted β -keto ester (3.1 g.), prepared from crystalline bromo compound, glacial acetic acid (6 c.c.) and 6N-HCl (6 c.c.), was refluxed for 12 hrs. After dilution with water (100 c.c.), the reaction mixture was extracted with ether. The organic layer was washed with a saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. The alkaline solution was worked up according to the method of Banerjee and Bhattacharyya (*loc. cit.*) to give an acidic material (2 g.) which was crystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether (40-60°), m.p. 80-82°, yield 1.6 g. Three crystallisations from the same solvent furnished the pure material, m.p. 88°; λ_{max} 236 μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.86). (Found: C, 65.69; H, 7.41. $C_{10}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 65.92; H, 7.73%).

The unsaturated substituted β -keto ester (3.5 g.), obtained from the liquid bromo compound, furnished on hydrolysis and decarboxylation an acid (1.8 g.), m.p. 72-75°. On recrystallisation, it furnished the pure material, m.p. 87-88°, the mixed m.p. of the latter remained undepressed when mixed with the above keto-acid.

Methyl β -(2-Keto-3-methyl-cyclohex- $\Delta^{1:5}$ -enyl)-propionate (VII: R=Me).—The above crude acid (51 g., m.p. 75-80°) was refluxed with a mixture of absolute methanol (100 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (10 c.c., d 1.84) for 30 hours to furnish the ester (36 g.), b.p. 115-20°/1 mm; n_D^{25} 1.4760; λ_{max} 232 μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.77). (Found: C, 67.32; H, 8.43. $C_{11}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 67.33; H, 8.2%).

Methyl β -(2-Keto-3-methyl-6-diethyl malonate-cyclohexyl)-propionate (IX: R=Me; $R_1=H$; $R_2=CO_2Et$; $R_3=Et$).—The condensation of the above unsaturated keto-ester (4 g.) with diethyl malonate (4.2 g.) in presence of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (0.02 g.) and absolute ethanol (10 c.c.), was allowed to proceed for 7 days according to the method of Banerjee and Bhattacharyya (*loc. cit.*). The reaction mixture furnished the desired product (0.8 g.), b.p. 190-95°/2 mm. (Found: C, 60.25; H, 7.62. $C_{18}H_{24}O_7$ requires C, 60.67; H, 7.91%).

Methyl β -(2-Keto-3-methyl-6-ethyl cyanoacetate-cyclohexyl)-propionate (IX: R=Me; $R_1=H$; $R_2=CN$; $R_3=Et$).—To a stirred solution of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (1.2 g.) and absolute ethanol (150 c.c.), cooled in an ice-salt mixture, was added dropwise ethyl cyanoacetate (82 g.). To the enolate after 15 minutes was added dropwise a solution of the unsaturated keto-ester (VI, 78.4 g.) in absolute ethanol (30 c.c.). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand in an ice-salt bath

for 2 hours and then at room temperature for 66 hours. The stirring was continued for 4 hours only. The deep red reaction mixture was worked up to furnish the condensation product (74.1 g.), b.p. 180-90°/1 mm. This cyano-ester is soluble in 10% NaOH solution. (Found: N, 4.53. $C_{18}H_{23}O_5N$ requires N, 4.52%).

The other different conditions for the same condensation are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

	Unsat. ester.	Ethyl cyanoacetate.	Ethanol.	Sodium.	Time.	% Yield.
1	10.5 g.	14.7 g.	25 c.c.	0.02 g.	60 hrs.	Nil
2	4.0	4.8	22	0.04	48	35.36
3	4.0	5.0	22	0.06	44	46.47
4	19.6	20.5	50	0.20	48	35.36

Methyl β-(2-Keto-3-methyl-3-carbomethoxy-6-ethyl cyanoacetate-cyclohexyl)-propionate (VIII).—The Michael condensation between the unsaturated keto-ester (VI, 10.1 g.) in absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) with ethyl cyanoacetate (10.5 g.) in presence of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (0.1 g.) and absolute ethanol (30 c.c.), was performed, as described before, by allowing the reaction to proceed for 66 hrs. The reddish brown reaction mixture was worked up to furnish a thick yellow oil (7.8 g.), b.p. 210-15°/0.4 mm. This condensation product is soluble in 10% NaOH solution. (Found: C, 58.75; H, 6.91. $C_{18}H_{23}O_7N$ requires C, 58.85; H, 6.85%).

Methyl β-(2-Keto-3-methyl-6-ethyl methylcyanoacetate-cyclohexyl)-propionate (IX: R=R₁=Me; R₂=CN; R₃=Et).—The methylation of the above cyano-ester (15.5 g.) in absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) was performed with sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (1.2 g.) and absolute ethanol (35 c.c.), and methyl iodide (14 c.c.) by refluxing for 5 hours (Banerjee and Bhattacharyya, *loc. cit.*). The reaction mixture was worked up with ether and cold 10% NaOH solution to give the desired product (10.3 g.), b.p. 185-90°/1 mm. (Found: N, 4.07. $C_{17}H_{25}O_5N$ requires N, 4.33%).

Methyl β-(2-Keto-3-methyl-6-methyl acetate-cyclohexyl)-propionate (IX: R=R₃=Me; R₁=R₂=H).—The cyano compound (IX: R=Me; R₁=H; R₂=CN; R₃=Et; 12.8 g.) was refluxed with HCl (conc., 120 c.c.) for 40 hours. The reaction mixture was worked up as described before. The glassy acidic material (8.6 g.) was esterified with an ethereal solution of diazomethane. The ester was worked up with ether and 5% NaOH solution to furnish the dimethyl keto-ester (6.9 g.), b.p. 155-60°/1 mm; n_D^{25} 1.4695. (Found: C, 61.92; H, 8.07. $C_{14}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 62.19; H, 8.21%).

Methyl β-(2-Keto-3-methyl-6-methyl α-propionate-cyclohexyl)-propionate (IX: R=R₁=R₃=Me; R₂=H).—The cyano-ester (IX: R=R₁=Me; R₂=CN; R₃=Et; 7.5 g.) was refluxed with HCl (conc., 75 c.c.) for 40 hrs. The acidic material (4.5 g.), thus obtained, was refluxed with a mixture of absolute methanol (25 c.c.) and H₂SO₄ (3.5 c.c., *d* 1.84) for 30 hours to furnish the ester (4.1 g.), b.p. 160-65°/1 mm; n_D^{24} 1.4660. (Found: C, 63.14; H, 8.60. $C_{13}H_{21}O_5$ requires C, 63.39; H, 8.51%).

2-Methyldecalin-1:6-dione (XII: R=H).—A mixture of sodium dust (0.8 g.), dry thiophene-free benzene (30 c.c.), the ester (IX: R=R₃=Me; R₁=R₂=H; 5.8 g.)

and two drops of methanol was refluxed in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 4 hrs. The reddish brown reaction mixture was decomposed with iced HCl and worked up to furnish the crude β -keto ester (5.2 g.) which gave an intense violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. The above β -keto ester was refluxed with a mixture of glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) and 6N-HCl (20 c.c.) in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 12 hrs. After dilution with water (50 c.c.), the reaction mixture was worked up with ether and sodium bicarbonate solution. After removal of the ether, the residue was distilled to give the diketone (1.3 g.), b.p. 115-20°/4 mm, which solidified on standing, m.p. 66-69°. Two crystallisations from petroleum ether furnished the pure material, m.p. 79°. (Found: C, 72.90; H, 8.95. $C_{11}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 73.30; H, 8.91%).

The diketone (0.15 g.) was converted into the mono-semicarbazone (0.2 g.), m.p. 205-208° (decomp.), by the pyridine method. Three crystallisations from methanol gave the pure material, m.p. 211° (decomp.). (Found: N, 17.61. $C_{12}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires N, 17.70%).

To the boiling suspension of the semicarbazone (0.12 g.), 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (0.2 g.) and methanol (10 c.c.) were added 5-6 drops of HCl (conc.) when a clear red solution was obtained. On concentration, a yellowish red precipitate (0.25 g.), m.p. 204-210° (decomp.), was obtained. It was chromatographed over alumina using benzene as the eluting solvent. Three crystallisations of the product (0.2 g.) from a mixture of 95% ethanol and ethyl acetate (1:1) furnished yellow crystals of bis-2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 220° (decomp.). (Found: N, 20.92. $C_{22}H_{24}O_8N_8$ requires N, 20.72%).

2:5-Dimethyldecalin-1:6-dione (XII: R=Me).—(a). A mixture of the keto-dimethyl ester (IX: R=R₁=R₂=Me; R₃=H; 2.8 g.), dry thiophene-free benzene (25 c.c.), two drops of absolute methanol and powdered sodium hydride (0.5 g.) was refluxed in an atmosphere of nitrogen until the evolution of hydrogen had ceased (usually 3 hrs.). The red reaction mixture was decomposed with iced dilute HCl and worked up to furnish a material (2.5 g.) which gave a violet colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. The β -keto ester was refluxed with 6N-HCl (40 c.c.) for 12 hours. The reaction product was worked up with ether and bicarbonate solution to give the desired diketone (1.2 g.), b.p. 120-25°/3 mm. The latter was evaporatively distilled at 80-85°/0.4 mm; n_D^{20} 1.4940; λ_{max} 3051m μ (log ϵ 2.56). (Found: C, 73.87; H, 9.42. $C_{12}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 74.22; H, 9.32%).

When a smaller quantity of sodium hydride (0.35 g.) was used in the above experiment, the yield of the desired diketone was 58%.

(b). To a suspension of sodium methoxide, prepared from sodium dust (0.8 g.) and absolute methanol (1.4 c.c.) under thiophene-free benzene (25 c.c.), was added a solution of the above keto-dimethyl ester (5.8 g.) in dry thiophene-free benzene (5 c.c.). The reaction mixture was refluxed in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 6 hrs. The reddish brown reaction mixture was worked up and heated with 6N-HCl (50 c.c.) to furnish the diketone (1.4 g.).

(c). A mixture of the keto-diester (5.6 g.), dry thiophene-free benzene (30 c.c.), sodium dust (0.8 g.) and two drops of absolute methanol was refluxed in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 3 hrs. The dark brown reaction mixture, after working up, furnished the crude β -keto ester (5 g.) which was refluxed with 2.7*N*-NaOH solution (22.5 c.c.) for 3 hrs. On working up, it gave the diketone (1.15 g.).

(d). An intimate mixture of the crude dicarboxylic acid (IX : R=R₂=k, s=H ; R₁=Me ; 4.5 g.) and freshly prepared dry lead carbonate (22.5 g.) was heated under nitrogen at 270-80° for 1 hour under reduced pressure (water aspirator). The temperature was then increased to 300° and the reaction was allowed to proceed for further 30 mins. The brown oily distillate was taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and dried. After removal of the solvent, the residue was distilled, b.p. 120-25°/3 mm, yield 1.5 g., n_D^{20} 1.4970. (Found : C, 73.98 ; H, 9.19. C₁₃H₁₈O₂ requires C, 74.22 ; H, 9.32%).

The above diketone (0.2 g.) was converted into the semicarbazone (0.35 g.), m.p. 218-20° (decomp.), by the pyridine method. Two crystallisations from methanol furnished the mono-semicarbazone, m.p. 226-27°, containing probably a little bis-semicarbazone. (Found : N, 17.52. C₁₃H₂₁O₂N₃ requires N, 16.71%).

The crude semicarbazone (0.25 g.) was converted into the red 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (0.5 g.) by the method described before. It was purified by chromatography and then crystallised thrice from a mixture of 95% ethanol and ethyl acetate (1:1) to yield orange-red bis-2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (0.3 g.), m.p. 224-25° (decomp.). (Found : N, 20.16. C₂₄H₂₆O₈N₈ requires N, 20.20%).

To a clear solution of 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (0.4 g.) in acetone-free methanol (5 c.c.) and a few drops of HCl (conc.) was added a solution of the above diketone (0.2 g.) in acetone-free methanol (2 c.c.). The reaction mixture was boiled for 10 minutes when a yellowish red precipitate was obtained. The crude D.N.P. (0.35 g.) was chromatographed and crystallised twice from a mixture of ethanol and ethyl acetate (1:1) to furnish yellow flakes of mono-2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (0.2 g.), m.p. 210-12° (decomp.). The mixed m.p. of mono- and bis-2:4 dinitrophenylhydrazones was 203-204° (decomp.). (Found : N, 14.83. C₁₈H₂₂O₅N₄ requires N, 14.96%).

2-Methyldecalin-1:6-diol (XIII : R=H).—To a suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (0.6 g.) in dry ether (30 c.c.) was added dropwise with shaking a solution of the 2-methyldecalin-1:6-dione (0.75 g.) in dry ether (10 c.c.), when a white precipitate was formed. A further quantity of dry ether (10 c.c.) was added and the reaction was allowed to proceed at room temperature for 48 hrs. The reaction mixture was decomposed with water, followed by 10% H₂SO₄ solution (50 c.c.). The ethereal layer was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted with ether. The combined extract was washed with a small quantity of water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of ether, the solid residue (0.75 g.), m.p. 172-75°, was crystallised twice from a mixture of ether and ethanol (1:1) to yield the pure diol, m.p. 179-80°. (Found : C, 71.71 ; H, 11.01. C₁₁H₂₀O₂ requires C, 71.71 ; H, 10.91%).

2:5-Dimethyldecalin-1:6-diol (XIII : R=Me).—The compound (XII : R=Me ; 0.95 g.) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride (1 g) in ether (75 c.c.). It

was worked up to furnish the semi-solid diol (0.85 g.) which was crystallised from a mixture of ethanol and ether to give the diol (0.4 g.); m.p. 144-45°. On recrystallisation from the same solvent-mixture it furnished needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 144-45°. (Found: C, 72.52; H, 10.80. $C_{13}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 72.71; H, 11.15%). The mother-liquor on concentration furnished a thick oil (0.45 g.).

2-Methylnaphthalene.—An intimate mixture of the diol (XIII: R=H; 0.6 g.) and fused powdered potassium hydrogen sulphate (3 g.) was introduced in a preheated chamber, maintained at 180°, and left there for 1 hour when an oily distillate collected. The reaction tube was evacuated (water pump) and the temperature raised to 200°. The oil (0.35 g.), thus obtained, was heated with a mixture of selenium (2 g.) and sulphur (0.25 g.) at 210-15° for 16 hours and then at 250-60° for 16 hours and finally at 280° for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was worked up with benzene. After evaporation of the solvent, the residue was evaporatively distilled at 150-60°/40 mm. The solid distillate (0.11 g.), m.p. 31-32°, did not depress the m.p. of an authentic sample of 2-methylnaphthalene. The 2-methylnaphthalene was converted in to the picrate, m.p. 114-15° which, when admixed with an authentic sample, did not depress the m.p.

1:6-Dimethylnaphthalene.—The above semi-solid diol (XIII: R=Me; 0.7 g.) was dehydrated with fused potassium hydrogen sulphate (3.5 g.), as described before, to furnish the unsaturated compound (0.45 g.) which was heated with a mixture of selenium (2.5 g.) and sulphur (0.3 g.), as described before. The reaction mixture was worked up to give an oily product (0.175 g.) which was converted into the picrate. On crystallisation from ethanol, it furnished the pure product, m.p. 113° (Weissgerber and Krüber, *Ber.*, 1919, 52, 349, record m.p. 114°). (Found: N, 10.69; Calc. for $C_{16}H_{16}O_7N_3$: N, 10.90%).

1-Hydroxy-2:5-dimethyl-decal-6-one (XIV).—(a). A mixture of the diketone (XII: R=Me; 2 g.), dry thiophene-free benzene (100 c.c.), freshly distilled ethyleneglycol (0.6 c.c.) and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.03 g.) was refluxed, using a Dean and Stark constant water separator and utilising a lump of fused calcium chloride to absorb the water separated. To the reaction mixture was added a further quantity of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.01 g.) and the refluxing was continued for 1 hour more. The cooled reaction mixture was poured into saturated sodium carbonate solution. After separation of the benzene layer, the aqueous layer was extracted twice with benzene. The combined extract was washed twice with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the residue (2.4 g.) in dry ether (30 c.c.) was added to a suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (1.5 g.) in dry ether (30 c.c.) with shaking. The occasional shaking was continued for 2 hours and the reaction was allowed to proceed at room temperature for 48 hrs. The reaction mixture was worked up as before and the residue (2.2 g.), thus obtained, was refluxed with a mixture of methanol (20 c.c.) and 1*N*- H_2SO_4 (10 c.c.) for 75 mins. After removal of most of the methanol on a steam-bath under reduced pressure (water pump), the residual liquid was diluted with water (50 c.c.) and the precipitated oil was thoroughly extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the oily residue (1.9 g.), λ_{max} 302 m μ

(log ϵ 2.43), was chromatographed over alumina (85 g.). The fractions eluted with petroleum ether (60-80°) were combined and evaporatively distilled at 80-85°/0.4 mm to give the diketone (0.4 g.), identified through its D.N.P. The fractions, eluted with a mixture of petroleum ether (60-80°) and benzene (1:1), were combined and evaporatively distilled at 95-98°/0.2 mm to give the hydroxy-ketone (1.4 g.), which was again evaporatively distilled at 105-110°/0.4 mm to furnish a heavy colorless oil, n_D^{20} 1.4968. (Found: C, 73.03; H, 10.28. $C_{17}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 73.45; H, 10.24%).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (0.15 g., m.p. 219-21° decomp) was prepared from the above hydroxy-ketone (0.1 g.) and purified through chromatography. Two crystallisations from a mixture of ethanol and benzene (1:1) furnished long yellow needles, m.p. 223-24° (decomp.). The mixed m.p. of the latter with the D.N.P. of the diketone (XII: R=Me) was 202-205° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.21. $C_{18}H_{24}O_4N_4$ requires N, 14.88%).

(b). To a solution of the semicarbazone of 2:5-dimethyldecalin-1:6-dione (m.p. 226-27°, 0.2 g.) in 50 c.c. of absolute ethanol, cooled in ice, was added finely powdered sodium borohydride (0.75 g.). The reaction mixture was shaken occasionally for 30 minutes when the sodium borohydride went into solution. Again, a further quantity of sodium borohydride (0.25 g.) was added and the reaction was allowed to proceed for 24 hours at room temperature. The reaction mixture was neutralised with 10% acetic acid and the volatile solvents were removed under reduced pressure (water pump). The residual material (0.25 g.), which could not be crystallised, was refluxed with 5% aqueous oxalic acid (40 c.c.) for 12 hrs. The cooled reaction mixture was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with a saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and dried. After removal of ether, the residue (0.06 g.) was evaporatively distilled at 105-110°/0.4 mm to furnish the hydroxy-ketone (0.04 g.). The latter was converted into the 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 223-24° (decomp.). (Found: N, 15.32. $C_{18}H_{24}O_4N_4$ requires N, 14.88%). The mixed m.p. of this D.N.P. and the D.N.P. of the aforementioned preparation was undepressed. The D.N.P. of the hydroxy-ketone was less soluble in benzene and more in ethanol compared to the D.N.P. of the diketone (XII: R=Me). Reduction of the above semicarbazone in tetrahydrofuran did not give any useful product.

1-Hydroxy-2:4b-dimethyl-7-keto-1:2:3:4:4a:4b:5:6:7:9:10:10a-dodecahydrophenanthrene (III).—To an ice-cold suspension of sodium methoxide, prepared from sodium dust (0.4 g.) and absolute methanol (0.7 c.c.), in dry thiophene-free benzene (10 c.c.) was added, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, a solution of the above hydroxy-ketone (XIV, 1.6 g.) and ethyl formate (1.6 c.c.) in dry thiophene-free benzene (5 c.c.) with shaking. The reaction mixture was shaken for 2 hours in the cold and then left at room temperature for 48 hours, when a brown viscous semi-solid mass precipitated out. To the reaction mixture iced water (25 c.c.) was added and the benzene layer was separated. The organic layer was washed twice with cold 2% NaOH solution. The combined alkaline solutions were cooled in ice and acidified with iced HCl. (dil.) The precipitated oil was extracted thoroughly with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water and saturated common salt solution and filtered through

anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the residue (1.8 g.), which gave an intense violet colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution, was dissolved in dry thiophene-free benzene (75 c.c.) and then treated with freshly distilled mono-methylaniline (1.8 c.c.). The benzene was slowly distilled from a boiling water-bath in the course of 1 hour. A fresh quantity of thiophene-free benzene (75 c.c.) was again added and the benzene was removed, as described before. This procedure was repeated for 5 hours and then the benzene was completely removed from the reaction mixture under reduced pressure (water pump). The yellowish brown residue was kept at $70-80^{\circ}/4$ mm for 30 mins. The dry viscous brown oily methylanilinomethylene compound (2.6 g.), which did not crystallise, decomposed when attempt was made to evaporatively distil it and did not give any positive ferric reaction.

To a stirred mixture of the methiodide, prepared from 1-diethylaminobutan-3-one (1.5 g.) and methyl iodide (1.5 c.c.), and a solution of the aforementioned crude methylanilinomethylene compound (2.6 g.) in a mixture of dry thiophene-free benzene (5 c.c.) and *tert.*-butanol (10 c.c.), cooled in an ice-bath, was added dropwise in an atmosphere of nitrogen a solution of potassium *tert.*-butoxide, prepared from potassium metal (0.6 g.) and *tert.*-butanol (15 c.c.). A further quantity of *tert.*-butanol (5 c.c.) was used to wash down the adhering butoxide. After completion of the addition, the stirring of the cooled reaction mixture was continued for 3 hours. The reaction was allowed to proceed at room temperature for 16 hrs. After refluxing the reaction mixture for 2 hours, the solvents were removed under reduced pressure (water pump) and the dark coloured residue was acidified with a solution of glacial acetic acid (3 c.c.) in water (100 c.c.). The resulting oily suspension was extracted thoroughly with a mixture of ether and benzene. The organic layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the residue (3.1 g.) was refluxed with 10% HCl solution (100 c.c.) in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 2 hrs. The cooled, dark brown reaction product was extracted with a mixture of ether and benzene. The organic layer was washed with water and dried. After evaporation of the solvent, the residue (2.1 g.) was refluxed with 8% KOH solution (50 c.c.) for 3 hrs. The resulting tarry suspension was cooled in ice and then acidified with HCl (cold, dil.) and extracted with the same solvent mixture. The organic layer was washed with water, dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and dried. After evaporation of the solvent, the tarry residue (.8 g.) was fractionated by evaporative distillation under 0.2 mm: (i) $50-100^{\circ}$ (0.5 g.), probably the hydroxy ketone; (ii) $125-30^{\circ}$ (0.3 g.), viscous opaque glassy material; (iii) $150-60^{\circ}$ (traces). Fraction (ii) was again evaporatively distilled to yield a low-boiling product, $90-95^{\circ}/0.2$ mm (0.05 g.) and the desired material (0.25 g.), b.p. $125^{\circ}/0.2$ mm, $\lambda_{\max}$ $241 m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.09). The latter was again evaporatively distilled very slowly for analysis; b.p. $130-35^{\circ}/0.4$ mm; $\lambda_{\max}$ $241 m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.07). (Found: C, 77.50; H, 9.97. $C_{15}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 77.36; H, 9.74%).

The above alkaline treatment with 10, 15 and 20% aqueous NaOH did not improve the yield of the desired $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone.

To a solution of the above tricyclic ketone (0.06 g.) in methanol (1 c.c.) was added a solution of 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (0.05 g.) in methanol (2 c.c.) contain-

ing one drop of HCl (conc.). The reaction mixture was boiled for 5 minutes when an orange-red precipitate was formed. The crude product (0.06 g.), m.p. 226-30° (decomp.) was chromatographed on alumina, using benzene. The crude solid, thus obtained, was crystallised four times from a mixture of methanol and ethyl acetate (1:1) to give deep orange crystals (0.014 g.), m.p. 243-44° (decomp.), λ_{max} 383 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.37). (Found: C, 61.55; H, 6.69; N, 13.19. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_3\text{N}_4$ requires C, 61.67; H, 6.58; N, 13.07%).

Methyl β -(2-Ethylenedioxy-3-methyl 6-methyl α -propionate-cyclohexyl)-propionate (X).—A mixture of the keto-diester (IX: R=R₁=R₂=Me; R₃=H; 9.5 g.), dry thiophene-free benzene (60 c.c.), freshly distilled ethyleneglycol (2.2 g.) and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.04 g.) was refluxed, using a Dean and Stark water separator, for 6 hrs. Another lot of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.02 g.) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for a further period of 1½ hrs. The reaction mixture was worked up, as described before, to give a heavy oil (9.5 g.) which was distilled, b.p. 150-55°/0.3 mm. This material (8.5 g.), on repeated fractional and evaporative distillations, furnished a colorless oil (0.5 g.), evaporatively distilling at 115-20°/0.3 mm; n_D^{20} 1.4734. (Found: C, 61.94; H, 8.82. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 62.19; H, 8.58%).

(On cyclisation of the bulk material with either sodium dust or sodium hydride in benzene, followed by working up of the reaction product with a saturated solution of sodium dihydrogen phosphate and hydrolysis with alkali, furnished a mixture of the diketone and 1-ethylenedioxy-2:5-dimethyldecal-6-one, evaporatively distilling at 110°/3 mm. (Found: C, 72.04, 72.73; H, 9.14, 9.40%). The latter was converted into the mono-2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone in acid solution, m.p. 210-12° (decomp.).

Methyl β -(2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-6-n:ethyl α -propionate-cyclohexyl)-propionate (XI).—A mixture of the above ester (IX: R=R₁=R₂=Me; R₃=H; 2.28 g.), methanol (10 c.c.) and a solution of NaOH (1.28 g.) in water (2 c.c.) was refluxed in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 3 hrs. The methanol was removed and the residue after dilution with water was extracted with ether. The alkaline solution was acidified with 6N-HCl and the precipitated oil was worked up. To a cooled solution of the acidic material (2 g.), thus obtained, dissolved in 2.71N-NaOH solution (3 c.c.) and water (18 c.c.), was added sodium borohydride (1 g.) and the reaction was allowed to proceed at room temperature for 16 hrs. The reaction mixture, after refluxing, in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 1 hour, was poured into iced HCl. The precipitated oil was worked up and the acidic material, thus obtained, was esterified with diazomethane in ethereal solution to furnish the ester (0.7 g.), evaporatively distilling at 115-20°/0.2 mm. (Found: C, 63.25; H, 9.25. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 62.90; H, 9.15%).

The cyclisation of the afore-mentioned hydroxy-ester either with sodium methoxide in benzene or with sodium methoxide or ethoxide in absolute alcohol, furnished the unchanged ester as the major component.

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